

Management of Educational Facilities and Quality Education Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract:

This study investigated the extent to which management of educational facilities relates to quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. Four research questions and four corresponding hypotheses were used to guide the study. This study adopted correlational research design. The population for the study consists of 522, principals and vice-principals that is, 261 principals and 261 vice-principals in the 261 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 200 principals and vice-principals were drawn through simple random sampling technique and used for the study. Two instruments titled “Education Facilities Scale” (EFC) and “Quality Education Delivery Scale” (QEDS) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts; one in measurement and evaluation and, two others in Educational Management based on face and content validities. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha Method and the reliability coefficient obtained were 0.71 for (EDC) and 0.81 for (QEDS) respectively. The researchers personally administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of research assistants (Head Teacher) in each sampled school, who were properly instructed on what to do. The instruments were retrieved immediately after administration. Data collect were analysed using person product moment correlation statistics for the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses were tested at 0.05 Alpha level of significance. It was found that, there is significant relationship between management of educational facilities (administrative, classroom, recreational, laboratory) and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State independently taken. Based on the findings of the study conclusion and recommendations were made.

Keywords: Management, Education, Educational Facilities and Quality Education Delivery.

Introduction

Education all over the world is a powerful instrument for effecting national growth and development through appropriate skills, knowledge, attitude and competencies acquired by individuals. However, government at various levels in different countries makes concerted efforts in order to provide quality education to its citizens.

Osundu (2016) stressed that quality education is the right type of education that captures all that an individual is supposed to learn at each stages of his/her schooling. Obasi (2015) saw quality education in terms of provision of appropriate educational content to be covered at each schooling stage in line with national educational objectives. It is the education that covers all necessary areas that need to be learnt by an individual in school. Quality education is not to an extent the physical facilities only but, also the nature of the content to be covered by teachers in school.

Furthermore, quality education delivery is the extent to which the objectives of learning has been achieved in terms of affecting positions behavioural change in a learner through covering the appropriate learning objectives (Sabatine, 2016). The delivery of quality education in school is the sole responsibility of teachers through covering appropriate learning areas of objectives.

Obuogu (2019) opined that equality education delivery is tied to appropriate instructional delivery by teachers in covering education objectives at each learning stage. However, government provides the necessary physical facilities and non-physical facilities for it to occur (Edem, 2020).

Nwailu (2016) explained observable positive behavioural change in learner is the best way to measure quality education delivery in a school. When there is consistent positive change in a learner(s) than the goal of education in terms of quality education delivery has been achieved. There are a lot of variable that could negatively or positively affect quality education delivery. Prominent among those variables is the management of education facilities.

Management is the control of what goes on in an institution in order to bring about desired goal. It entails directing, handling, or running an institution which involves planning organizing, coordinating control and guiding what goes on, what people do and the use of facilities or materials to bring about the desirable change in an institution (Opara & Nwebo, 2014). Management of educational facilities involves proper planning, control and coordination of education facilities for effective use in achieving educational objectives.

Educational facilities are those human and non-human facilities that are necessarily required for effective teaching and learning in a school (Obialika, 2019). But, this study focused on the non-human facilities which include administration facilities, classroom facilities, recreational facilities and laboratory facilities. Administrative facilities are those resource that helps in the day to day growth running of school and they include administration buildings, staff, offices, chairs, desk, and office materials etc. Ojo (2017) noted that administrative facilities involves all that a school requires for achievement of educational goal. Classroom Facilities includes projectors, classroom chairs, desk, teaching aids etc.

Ofoji (2018) explained that management of classroom facilities is a necessary variables in order to achieve educational goal. Recreational facilities are those resources that enhance the physical and psycho-motor wellbeing of a learner-which are also part of learning experience. They include school field, volley ball court and table tennis etc.

Laboratory facilities include science and art facilities used in teaching and learning such as text books, clerical desk, and apparatus in the laboratory. Madu (2014) stressed that proper management laboratory facilities promotes adequate teaching and learning.

Meanwhile Okoh (2019) noted that there are many variables that could alter positively or negatively quality education delivery in school. Quality education delivery remains important factor in measuring academic achievement of a learner in school. It is this background that the resources intended to study management of educational facilities and quality education delivery in public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State.

Review of Related Literature

Management involves deliberate planning, directing and coordinating the affairs or activities of an institution to achieve a desirable positive goal (Ihejirika, 2019). Educational facilities involves all the physical facilities that enhance job performance and quality education delivery in a school. Meanwhile quality education delivery is the success recorded in achieving educational objective observable through behavioural change in a learner (Mark, 2017).

However, the information and decision-making theory developed by cox and blade in (199) is the theoretical anchor based of this study. This is because the theory emphasized on the compositi ermine the organizational goal (Openi 2017).

Onuka (2018) investigated the relationship between provision of administrating facilities and job performance of teachers in public Senior Secondary School a significant relationship was found in the study. Sabatstine (2016) found a significant influence of classroom management on academic performance of Secondary School Students based on school location.

Statement of the Problem

The essence of education is to enhance quality well-being of the learner and the society at large through teaching and learning. However despite the efforts of the government and non-governmental agencies, in terms of provision of educational facilities for teaching and learning inform of provision human and non-human facilities such as constant recruitment of teachers, provision of laboratory and library facilities, building for teaching and learning, staff offices and health care facilities etc. Not much has be done in terms

of its long term management for positive educational out-come as noticed in recent times by the researchers especially, in most public senior secondary school in Rivers State. Most of these educational facilities are not well managed by school administrators for the betterment of the beneficiaries and, this situation is to a large extent contributing to poor quality of education delivery in most schools in the area.

Teachers now teach without the required learning instructional materials and other facilities that well give then required psychological comfort for the teaching. Also these situation affects the required behaviour out-come of learners in terms of positive change after learning. The question remains that, does management of educational facilities have any relationship to quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the extent to which management of educational facilities relates to quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. The objectives are to:

1. determine the relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
2. investigate the relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
3. ascertain the relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
4. find out the relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide this study:

1. What is the extent of the relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?
3. What is the extent of the relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?
4. What is the extent of the relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance were used to guide the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
4. There is no significant relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopted correlational research design. The population for the study consists of 522, principals and vice-principals that is, 261 principals and 261 vice-principals in the 261 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 200 principals and vice-principals were drawn through simple random sampling technique and used for the study. Two instruments titled “Education Facilities Scale” (EFC) and “Quality Education Delivery Scale” (QEDS). The instruments contained 29 items for (QEDS) which were structured based on four point of strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Agree which were used for data

collection. The instruments were validated by three experts; one in measurement and evaluation and, two others in Educational Management based on face and content validities. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha Method and the reliability coefficient obtained were 0.71 for (EDC) and 0.81 for (QEDS) respectively.

The researcher personally administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of research assistants (Head Teacher) in each sampled school, who were properly instructed on what to do. The instruments were retrieved immediately after administration. Data collect were analysed using person product moment correlation statistics for the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses were tested at 0.05 Alpha level of significance.

Results

The results of the Analyses were presented in the tables as follows:

Research Question 1: What is the extent of the relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant between management of administration facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Table 1: Shows Pearson product moment correlation analysis on the relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery.

Variables	N	df	r	p	Alpha Level	Result
Management of administrative facilities	200	198	.73	.000	0.05	Significant
Quality education delivery						

Table 1 above, indicates that the correlation coefficient (r-value) is .73. The result is that, there is high positive relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery. The result is significant (p-value) at .000, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that, the null hypothesis is rejected, alternating accepted. The result therefore is that, there is significant relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of the relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Table 2: Shows Pearson product moment correlation analysis on the relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery.

Variables	N	df	r	p	Alpha Level	Result
Management of classroom facilities	200	198	.64	.000	0.05	Significant
Quality education delivery						

Table 2 above, indicates that the correlation coefficient (r-value) is .64. The result is that, there is high positive relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery. The result is significant (p-value) at .000, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that, the null hypothesis is rejected, alternating accepted. The result therefore is that, there is significant relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of the relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Table 3: Shows Pearson product moment correlation analysis on the relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery.

Variables	N	df	r	p	Alpha Level	Result
Management of recreational facilities	200	198	.79	.000	0.05	Significant
Quality education delivery						

Table 3 above, indicates that the correlation coefficient (r-value) is .79. The result is that, there is high positive relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery. The result is significant (p-value) at .000, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that, the null hypothesis is rejected, alternating accepted. The result therefore is that, there is significant relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Research Question 4: What is the extent of the relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State?

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Table 4: Shows Pearson product moment correlation analysis on the relationship between management of recreational laboratory facilities and quality education delivery.

Variables	N	df	r	p	Alpha Level	Result
Management of laboratory facilities	200	198	.77	.000	0.05	Significant
Quality education delivery						

Table 4 above, indicates that the correlation coefficient (r-value) is .77. The result is that, there is high positive relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery. The result is significant (p-value) at .000, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This implies that, the null hypothesis is rejected, alternating accepted. The result therefore is that, there is significant relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study were summarized as follows:

1. There is significant relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
2. There is significant relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
3. There is significant relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.
4. There is significant relationship between management of laboratory facilities and quality education delivery public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of finding were as follows:

The result of research question one and hypotheses one indicates that; there is significant relationship between management of administrative facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. This indicates that, while the scores of administrative facilities were increasing, the scores of that quality education delivery were also increasing. This also implies that effective control of administrative facilities enhances quality education out-come in school.

This finding is in agreement with that of Onuka (2018) who found that there is significant relationship between provision of administrative facilities and job performance of teachers in public senior secondary school.

The finding of research question two and hypothesis two revealed that, there is significant relationship between management of classroom facilities and quality education delivery of public senior secondary school in Rivers State. This also implies that as the scores of classroom facilities were increasing other scores of quality education delivery were also increasing. The classroom facilities contributes much in the quality of education actualization in school. This finding is supported by that of Sabastine (2016) who found that there is significant influence of classroom management on academic performance of students based on school location.

The finding of research question three and hypothesis three shows that, there is significant relationship between management of recreational facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. This indicates that as the scores of recreational facilities were increasing the cores of quality education delivery were also increasing.

This also implies that when recreational facilities are well managed it enhance quality education delivery in school. This finding is collaborated by that of Okon (2019) who found that there is significant relationship between school facilities and job performance of teachers in secondary school.

The finding of research question four and hypothesis four revealed that there is significant relationship between management laboratory facilities and quality education delivery in public senior secondary school in Rivers State. This means that as the scores of laboratory facilities were increasing the scores quality education delivery were also increasing. This also implies that there is need for proper utilization of laboratory facilities in school. This finding is in agreement with that of Jerome (2021) who found that laboratory facilities predicts services delivery of teachers in school.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study it was concluded that administrative facilities, classroom facilities, recreational facilities and laboratory facilities significantly relates with quality education delivery in public school in Rivers State. Therefore, educational facilities play a major in quality education delivery in public school.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Government should constantly provide adequate human and non-human facilities in the secondary education sector, as this will increase the achievement of quality education delivery at all time.
2. Non-Governmental agencies should always help through free will donation to schools in the provision of infrastructural facilities that will enhance quality education delivery in our schools.
3. Ministry of education through its department for equality assurance should always carry-out their functions effectively by recommending to the government on appropriate facilities that will enhance quality educational delivery in the school system.
4. School administrators and teachers should always ensure good protection and effective use of education facilities for successful achievement of quality education delivery in the education sector.

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